
ABSTRACT

The main aim of this project is to study the structural and transport properties of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ at ($x=0.1$ and 0.15). The brief discussion on the progress of this project is given that the samples were characterized using x-ray diffraction (XRD) technique. This gives the information of the crystal symmetry, structure and lattice parameters, which varies with the Te concentration. Further, the electrical resistivity data, which confirm the effect of carrier doping in the system, was analyzed. The resistivity data was also fitted in the Mott's variable range hopping (VRH) model in the high temperature regime, as a result of those processes the unit cell volume of the sample decrease with the increase in Te concentration, the crystallite size increases with the increase in Te concentration. On decreasing the temperature this $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ first undergoes insulating to metallic phase transition at transition temperatures $T_p=203$ and 209oK respectively, then resuming the semiconducting behavior, the samples are found to be in single phase. The charge ordering transition temperature of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ is enhanced within Te concentration ($T_{co}=125$ to 135oK), the magneto resistance as a function of temperature is also studied in the presence of magnetic of the magnetic fields.

KEYWORDS: Provkite material, $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$, Mott's VRH model, x-ray diffraction, temperature dependence of magneto-resistance (MR), optical, magnetic, thermoelectric power and dc conduction measurement.

INTRODUCTION

Transition metal oxides (TMO's) constitute one of the most fascinating classes of inorganic solid exhibiting structural, electrical transport, magnetic and optical properties, occurring due to the strong electron correlation effect in the systems. Further, TMO's possess some interesting phenomenon such as high Te superconductivity in cuprite system, metal insulator transition (MIT), colossal magneto resistance (CMR) and charge ordering in manganites [26].

In particular, the existence of metal-insulator transition phenomenon in La- based manganites was established in early 1950s [9,12] and was extensively studied thereafter. These types of perovskites present a very interesting group of materials because of extremely rich variety of their electrical properties from a large gap insulator to metal and magnetic properties such as nonmagnetic to magnetism, anti-ferromagnetism to ferromagnetism. Examples of these perovskites are LaFeO_3 , LaCoO_3 , LaCrO_3 , LaNiO_3 , LaMnO_3 and certain doped manganites. The magnetic and electrical transport properties of these samples are determined by several factors such as the percentage of the divalent ions, the ionic radii of the metal ions, and the method used in preparation of samples [7,10].

Basically the name provkite refers to a relatively rare mineral called as calcium titanium oxide (CaTiO_3) occurring in orthorhombic crystal symmetry and it is found in contact metamorphic rocks and associated mafic intrusives neophelinesyenites and rare carbonates. The basic chemical formula follows the pattern ABO_3 in which A and B are cations of different size e.g. LaMnO_3 , more specifically, A is a rare earth element and B is transition metal element.

Figure 1. General perovskite structure(BCC)

The general crystal structure can be thought of as a body centered cubic (BCC) lattice with 'A' ion of valency +2 at the center surrounded by eight 'B' ion of valency +4 each at the corner at 12 'O' ions each occupies the edge.

Figure 2. General perovskite structure(FCC)

The structure can be thought of as face centered cube (FCC) lattice with ion 'B' at the center surrounded by six 'O' ions, each at a face center and eight 'A' ions, each at the center[5].

For perovskite itself CaTiO_3 cubic symmetry is found at all temperatures but for compounds such as BaTiO_3 , PbTiO_3 , KNbO_3 there is slight adjustment to a tetragonal form of cooling below the ferroelectric transition temperature. The stability of a perovskite structure depends upon tolerance factor defined Goldschmidt tolerance factor and is formulated as:

$$t = (R_A + R_O) / [\sqrt{2}R_B + R_O]$$

Where R_A , R_B and R_O are ionic radii of A, B cation and oxygen respectively. However, for an ideal perovskite $t=1$ and for $t < 1$, the cubic structure which leads to deviation in Mn-O-Mn bond angle from 180 degree (a case for ideal perovskite) the deviation of Mn-O-Mn bond angle from 180 degree leads to distortion in MnO_6 octahedra, for instance LaMnO_3 is an orthorhombic perovskite structure and is an insulator[17].

Generally, the electrical and magnetic properties of these perovskites depend on the choice of elements A, B and doping element either at A or B site [2]. Moreover, perovskite structure has the curious property that the central atom does not touch its coordination neighbors in violation of Pauling's rules. This gives the structure, the property of piezoelectricity and sometime Ferro electricity. Oxides such as BaTiO_3 , LaNiO_3 , LaMnO_3 , LaFeO_3 etc, are known as representative compounds. These materials offer wide variety of phase transition like ferroelectric to antiferroelectric or purely structural transition. Most of the transition encountered in the perovskite crystal involves only a small change in the atomic position parameters, changes that leave the essential topology of the structure unaltered. These changes are often hard to detect directly and are detected indirectly by the changes or discontinuities in physical properties that are linked to the changes of atomic position parameter [1,22].

NATURE AND BEHAVIOR OF PEROVSKITE MATERIALS

Recently, a promising class of magnetic material with composition $R_{1-x}A_xMnO_3$ ($R=La, Nd, Gd, Y$; $A=Ca, Sr, Ba, Pb$) has been identified. Most of the studies in these materials were done by replacing La by divalent elements. The basic structural, magnetic and transport properties of oxides $La_{1-x}A_xMnO_3$ ($A=Ca, Sr, Ba, Pb$) were widely studied. Recently, tetravalent cation doped manganites, including Ce, Sn, Te, Zr have gradually attracted much attention since such tetravalent cation doping may drive the valence state of Mn^{3+} in the parent compound into the mixed state of Mn^{3+} and Mn^{2+} . This is known as electron doping and such compounds are known as the electron doped manganites [14,15].

Generally, all the manganese ions in $LaMnO_3$ family compound are considered as in a mixed valence state of Mn^{3+} - Mn^{4+} ion has electron configuration of $t_{2g}^3 e_g^1$. The low energy t_{2g} triplet state contribute a local spin of $S=3/2$, while e_g electron is either itinerant electrons hop between Mn^{3+} and Mn^{4+} , and the hopping probability depends on Mn-O-Mn bond angle and relative orientation of the local spin. This kind of physical picture can be qualitatively depicted in the CMR manganite resistance behavior [28].

Later on, some reports on Ce doped $LaMnO_3$ appeared in the $La_{1-x}Ce_xMnO_3$ system, where Ce is a tetra-valent ion, was electron-doped system. The reports suggested that the CMR behavior probably occurred in a system of mixed valence state Mn^{2+} - Mn^{3+} . Therefore, it is of great interest to investigate whether the CMR effect exists in the compounds in which La^{3+} is partially replaced by tetra-valence element [29].

THEORY

The basis for the theoretical understanding of Mn oxides is usually the concept of the double exchange (DE) that consider the exchange of electron between neighboring Mn^{3+} and Mn^{4+} sites with strong on-site Hund's coupling. Perturbative calculation carried out by Millis et al. showed that DE alone could not explain the experimental data of Mn oxides and suggested that a strong Jahn-Teller distortion should be responsible for the transport properties. [1, 8] Later on it was suggested that the localization effect [4, 6] in the double exchange model based upon non perturbative treatment might be able to account for the novel properties of manganites. The theory of variable range hopping has been quite successful in describing the conductivity in insulating sample, due to Mott [5,27] who formulated an approach using ideas from percolation theory. A good discussion of Mott's original approach also appears in [26].

In general Mott's VRH model describes the low temperature behavior of the resistivity in strongly disordered system where states are localized. Consider two states located a distance R apart. The state on the left hand side is at energy E_1 and that on the right hand side is at energy E_2 . Suppose $W = E_2 - E_1 > 0$. An electron can hop from left to right by the absorption of phonon with energy ω . The hopping rate is given by:

$$\frac{1}{\tau_R} = \omega_0 e^{-2r/a} f_1 (1 - f_2) n(W) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where ω_0 , is the attempt frequency which is given by typical phonon frequency. A is the localization length, $n(W)$ is the Bose factor and $f_i = \frac{1}{e^{(E_i - \mu_i)/kT} + 1}$ is the Fermi factor for states $i=1$ and 2 with chemical potential μ_1 and μ_2 . The hopping rate for right to left by the emission of phonons is:

$$\frac{1}{\tau_L} = \omega_0 e^{-2r/a} f_2 (1 - f_1) \{n(W) + 1\} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

The current is:

$$I = eR \left[\frac{1}{\tau_R} - \frac{1}{\tau_L} \right] \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Current in terms of chemical potential:

$$I = \frac{eR\omega_0}{kT} e^{-W/kT} e^{-2r/a} (\mu_1 - \mu_2) \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

With the help of above we can found the expression for the conductance as

$$G = \frac{e^2 R \omega_0}{kT} e^{-W/kT} e^{-2r/a} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

The key insight to Mott is that G should be determined by optimizing the competition between the overlap term $e^{-2r/a}$, which favors short hops and the energy activation W/kT , which favours long hops. With longer hops; one has a better chance of reducing the activation energy W . We estimate W by the typical energy level spacing in volume with radius R .

$$W = \frac{3}{4\pi r^3 N(E_F)} \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

Where $N(E_F)$ is the density of states at Fermi energy. By substituting the value of W from Eq. 6 in 5 we find:

$$\bar{R}^4 = \frac{9a}{4\pi N(E_F)kT} \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

And the conductance

$$G \approx \exp(-T/T_0)^{\frac{1}{4}} \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

Where T_0 is related to the average energy spacing in a volume a^3 as:

$$kT_0 = \frac{1}{N(E_F)a^3} \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

Eq. 8 is the famous Mott's variable range hopping (VRH) law [20]

The electrons in a solid interact both with one another and with the lattice vibrations. Interaction with phonons also has an important effect, particularly in transition metal oxides, i.e. they interact with the electrons or holes in a narrow band semiconductor or semimetal, forming polarons.

The behavior of polarons is of great importance in particular to transition metal oxides. In the polar material a polaron is the region round an electron in the conduction band in which the material is polarized by the electron, as first proposed by Landau (1993). The field in vicinity of the electron, with which it interacts, has a potential energy function:

$$V(r) = -\frac{e^2}{k_p r}, r > r_p \dots \dots \dots (10)$$

$$= -\frac{e^2}{k_p r_p}, r > r_p$$

Where $1/k_p = 1/k_\infty - 1/k$ and k_∞, k are the high frequency and static dielectric constants in principle. The radius of polaron, r_p , is determined by minimizing the polaron's energy. Which is made up of the energy of the electron in a polaron well

$$= -\frac{e^2}{k_p r_p} + \frac{\hbar^2 \pi^2}{2m^* r_p^2} \dots \dots \dots (11)$$

Where m^* is the effective mass. The energy required to polarize the medium

$$= \frac{1}{2} e^2 / k_p r_p$$

If r_p is larger than the lattice parameter, the polaron is called a large or Fröhlich polaron and its properties depend on the dimensionless coupling constant α , defined by

$$\alpha^2 = \left(\frac{e^2}{k_p}\right) \sqrt{\left(\frac{m^*}{3\hbar^3 \omega_0}\right)} \dots \dots \dots (12)$$

The polaron is called small polaron when r_p has its limiting size,

$$r_p = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\pi}{6N}\right)^{1/3} \dots \dots \dots (13)$$

Where N is number of sites per unit volume. The energy of small polaron $-W_p$ is given by

$$W_p = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{e^2}{k_p r_p}\right) \dots \dots \dots (14)$$

The small polaron has the following properties:

At high temperature [$T > \frac{1}{2} \theta_D$] it moves by 'hopping'. The frequency with which it 'hops' from one site to another is given by the relation.

$$\omega = \exp\left(\frac{-W_H}{kT}\right) \dots \dots \dots (15)$$

Where

$$W_H = \frac{e^2}{4k_p} \left(\frac{1}{r_p} - \frac{1}{R}\right) \dots \dots \dots (16)$$

And R is the distance from one site to another, W_H is the energy of intermediate state, where thermal fluctuation have decreased the depth of the potential well and produced an empty potential well on neighborhood site so that an electron can resonate between the two wells. Equation 16 is valid only in so called adiabatic approximation, which means that an electron can go backwards and forward several times during the period when the two wells have the same depth.

At low temperatures, $T < \frac{1}{2}\theta_D$, the electron moves from site to site without the aid of thermal activation. At zero point energy $\frac{1}{2}\hbar\omega$ due to thermal vibration, the hoping frequency becomes:

$$\omega = \exp\left(\frac{-W_H}{\frac{1}{2}\hbar\omega}\right) \dots \dots \dots (17)$$

It can be seen from elementary considerations, the distortion of surrounding medium which leads to intermediate state with energy W_H can be described by simple harmonic motion, with a parameter ξ for the displacement, a potential energy $\frac{1}{2}p\xi^2$ and a wave function of the form $\psi = \text{const} \exp(-\alpha\xi^2)$. The probability $|\psi|^2$ for a configuration with potential energy W_H is thus:

$$\exp\left(\frac{-2\alpha W_H}{\frac{1}{2}p}\right) \dots \dots \dots (18)$$

And putting in the constant it is easy to see that:

$$\frac{4\alpha}{p} = \left(\frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}\hbar\omega}\right) \dots \dots \dots (19)$$

Energy level scheme of LaMnO3 and Jahn Teller distortion and effect

In LaMnO3, Mn exists in +3 states (3d4). There are four electrons in d-orbital. Due to crystal field splitting 3 electrons go to 't2g' level and the remaining one electron goes to 'eg' level. We know that Jahn-Teller distortion will be effective only when 'eg' orbitals are asymmetrically filled here 'eg' orbital contain only one electron i.e. asymmetrically filled and it is, thus, Jahn-Teller active. Due to this Jahn-Teller distortion the MnO6 octahedra distort in such a way that there are long and short Mn-O bonds [15,22]. This occurs below a characteristic temperature (Tjt). Due to this JT distortion the oxygen ion is displaced by $\geq 0.1\text{\AA}$, splitting of the 'eg' level occurs and opens a gap at Fermi level [28,29].

Figure 3. Energy level of scheme for LaMnO3

In Figure 3, we have shown a schematic of the band diagram of LaMnO3 that elucidate how JT distortion splits the conduction band makes the material insulating.

Effect of doping in Manganites and Zener Double Exchange Interaction

Generally manganites Mn exists in three states Mn⁺², Mn⁺³ and Mn⁺⁴ in orthorhombically distorted octahedral with 3d⁵, 3d⁴ and 3d³ configuration respectively. The doping of a divalent cation at the rare earth site converts a proportionate amount of Mn⁺³ ion into Mn⁺⁴ i.e. Mn⁺³-Mn⁺⁴ system have been obtained. We have already known that in Mn⁺³ system there is single electron in (⁵e_g) and is J-T active. On the other hand Mn⁺⁴ ion has no 'eg' electron as all 3 electrons go to the 't_{2g}' level. Therefore there is rise to a vacancy (hole) in the Mn⁺³-Mn⁺⁴ system. Due to strong correlation effect the 't_{2g}' electrons are localized where the 'eg' electrons can hop depending on the relative configuration of the local spins. The hopping of 'eg' electron can be demonstrated by Double Exchange Interaction [14, 15, 22]

Figure 4. Double Exchange Model

Here an electron from Mn⁺³ jumps to Mn⁺⁴ via the oxygen ion. According to the Double Exchange Interaction the electron movement from one species to another will be facilitated more easily if the electrons do not have to change spin direction in order to conform with Hund's rules when on the accepting species. The jump of electron from one species to another species leads to increase of conductivity and it also leads to ferromagnetic alignment of neighboring ions.

On the other hand if tetravalent ion (Zr⁺⁴) ion is doped a proportionate amount of Mn⁺³ ion is likely to be converted into divalent state Mn⁺² that is Mn⁺³-Mn⁺⁴ system is obtained. In this case there is one electron in the 'eg' band corresponding to Mn⁺³. But for Mn⁺²(3d⁵) there is no first order crystal field splitting as for d⁵ term not crystal field stabilization is zero. Thus, in such a system the interaction between the 'eg' electron and the 'd' electron should be large that would cause a change in CMR effect[2].

Experimental Methods:

In order to determine the structure of different crystals a highly significant law in solid state physics is Bragg's Law. Crystals are composed of various intersecting planes each of which itself contains a number of atoms. Since the interatomic separations in crystals are of the same order of magnitude as the wavelength of x-ray crystals act as diffraction gratings and produce diffraction on being irradiated by x-ray.

If each plane were perfectly reflecting, only the first plane of a parallel set would see the radiation and any wavelength would be reflected, but each plane reflects 10⁻³ to 10⁻⁵ of the incident radiation, so that 10³ to 10⁵ planes may contribute to the formation of Bragg's reflected beam in a perfect crystal.

The x-ray gets diffracted from the crystal planes when the Bragg's condition is satisfied i.e. $2d\sin\theta = n\lambda$. Where d is the interplanar spacing, n is the order of diffraction, λ is the wavelength of x-ray and θ is the glancing angle.

By measuring 2θ one can determine the spacing d between the planes in the crystal. The diffraction pattern gives us information about the average particle/ grain size, lattice parameters, crystal structure of the sample etc.

Figure 5. The schematic of x-ray diffractometer

Figure 3, shows that the XRD patterns are recorded with diffractometer. X-ray diffraction (XRD) is a powerful tool for studying both x-ray spectra and the arrangement of atoms in crystals. To study the spectra, a particular set of crystal planes having a known spacing 'd' is chosen. These planes effectively reflect different wavelengths at different angles. A detector that can discriminate one angle from another can then be used to determine the wavelength of radiation reaching it. The crystal itself can be studied with a monochromatic x-ray beam, to determine not only the spacing of various crystal planes but also the structure of the unit cell. The recorded diffraction pattern gives the intensity versus 2θ plot.

Most common way of measuring the resistivity of a semiconducting material is the four-point collinear probe method.

Figure 6. Four pint collinear probe resistivity configuration

Figure 4, shows the technique that involves bringing four equally spaced probes in contact with a material of unknown resistance. The probe array is placed in the center of the material. The two outer probes are used for sourcing current and the two inner probes are used for measuring the resulting voltage drop across the surface of the sample. The volume resistivity is calculated as follows:

$$\rho = \frac{\pi}{\ln 2} \times \frac{V}{I} \times t \times k$$

Where, ρ represent volume resistivity, V represent the measured voltage, I represent the source current, t represent the sample thickness and k represent a correction factor based on the ratio of the probe of wafer diameter and on the ratio of wafer thickness to probe separation.

The resistivity of the semiconductor is often determined using this technique. Four probes eliminate measurement errors due to the probe resistance, the spreading resistance under each probe and the contact resistance between each metal probe and semiconductor material. Because a high impedance voltmeter draws little current, the voltage drops across the resistance, spreading resistance and contact resistance are very small.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The structural parameters were refined by the standard rietveld technique [32]. The calculated parameters of prepared sample for $x=0.10$, 0.15 are shown in Figure 7, and tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Lattice parameters and unit cell volume of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.10$ and 0.15) at room temperature.

Composition	$\frac{a}{\text{Å}}$	$\frac{b}{\text{Å}}$	$\frac{c}{\text{Å}}$	Type of the unit cell	Volume (nm ³)
$\text{La}_{0.90}\text{Te}_{0.10}\text{MnO}_3$	5.526	5.526	13.350	Hexagonal	353.03
$\text{La}_{0.85}\text{Te}_{0.15}\text{MnO}_3$	5.524	5.524	13.351	Hexagonal	352.80

Figure 7. Power XRD pattern of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.10$)

Figure 7, shows at the room temperature x-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.10$) confirmed single phase nature of the sample with a few secondary phase peaks. This is consistent with many earlier reports on electron doped manganites [13,19]. The lattice parameters (a , b , c) with the values (5.526, 5.526, 13.350) Å respectively, rhombohedral (Hexagonal) crystal structure with space group $R\bar{3}c$, while the crystalline size of the sample is 34.60 nm and the volume was 353.03 nm³.

Figure 8. Power XRD pattern of $La_{1-x}Te_xMno(x=0.15)$

Figure 8, shows at the room temperature x-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of $La_{1-x}Te_xMno(x=0.10)$ confirmed single phase nature of the sample with a few secondary phase peaks. This is consistent with many earlier reports on electron doped manganites [13,19]. The lattice parameters (a, b, c) with the values (5.524, 5.524, 13.351)Å respectively, rhombohedral (Hexagonal) crystal structure with space group R3c, while the crystalline size of the sample is 37.76nm and the volume was 352.80nm³

Figure 9. Shows that in $\rho(T)$ as a function of $1/T^{1/4}$ for $La_{0.90}Te_{0.10}MnO_3$.

Figure 9, shows that in $\rho(T)$ as a function of $1/T^{1/4}$ for $La_{0.90}Te_{0.10}MnO_3$. The resistivity $\rho(T)$ data showed to be fitted with purely activated conduction model. $\rho(T) = \rho_0(T) \exp(E_a/kBT)$, three dimensional Mott's variable range hopping (VRH) model [20,21], $\rho(T) = \rho_0(T) \exp(T_0/T)^{1/\gamma}$, with $\gamma = 4$, predicting the charge transport by tunneling of electrons or holes [36], $\gamma = 4$ has been considered as an indicative for isotropic charge transport.

Figure 10. Shows that in $\rho(T)$ as a function of $1/T^{1/4}$ for $La_{0.85}Te_{0.15}MnO_3$.

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Table 2. Values of characteristic temperature t_0 , density of states at the Fermi energies $N(E_F)$ and chi-square (χ^2) determined from fitting of resistivity–temperature data for $La_{1-x}Te_xMnO_3$ ($x = 0.10$ and 0.15).

Concentration	Temperature ranges	$t_0(K)$	$N(E_F)(eV^{-1}.cm^{-3})$	χ^2
0.10	Above $\rho(T)$	560×10^5	2.09×10^{26}	0.9996
	$T > T_{CO}$	485×10^4	2.42×10^{27}	0.9959
	$T_N < T < T_{CO}$	7.86	1.49×10^{33}	0.9800
	$T < T_N$	437.71	2.68×10^{31}	0.9996
0.15	Above $\rho(T)$	660×10^5	1.78×10^{26}	0.9985
	$T > T_{CO}$	677×10^4	1.74×10^{27}	0.9952
	$T_N < T < T_{CO}$	7.7	1.52×10^{33}	0.9240
	$T < T_N$	1923.48	6.11×10^{30}	0.9965

Figure 11. Temperature dependence of magneto-resistance (MR) measured in the presence of magnetic field of 1T, 5T and 8T for $La_{1-x}Te_xMnO_3$ ($x=0.10$).

Figure 11, shows that at fitting of resistivity temperature data for $La_{1-x}Te_xMnO_3$ ($x=0.10$) various temperature range occurs. The values of characteristic temperature T_0 can be given as the following above T_p we got $560 \times 10^5 K$, density of state at the Fermi energies [28] was 2.09×10^{26} and the chi-square χ^2 was 0.9996. Similarly when $T > T_{CO}$, $T_N < T < T_{CO}$ and $T < T_N$ as shown in Table 2. In the presence of the magnetic fields [8T, 5T, 1T], sharp and broad peaks can be attributed to the co-existence of the antiferromagnetic and ferromagnetic clusters, the phase co-existence features is explained in the frame work of electronic phase separation scenario, predicated for the manganites [3]. This behavior is attributed to the structural inhomogeneity's characteristic of ceramic sample that governs the electric and magnetic properties.

Figure 12. Temperature dependence of magneto-resistance (MR) measured in the presence of magnetic field of 1T, 5T and 8T for $La_{1-x}Te_xMnO_3$ ($x=0.15$).

Figure 12, shows that at fitting of resistivity temperature data for $La_{1-x}Te_xMnO_3$ ($x=0.15$) various temperature range occurs. The values of characteristic temperature T_0 can be given as the following above T_p we got $660 \times 10^5 K$, density of state at the Fermi energies [28] was 1.78×10^{26} and the chi-square χ^2 was 0.9985. Similarly when $T > T_{CO}$, $T_N < T < T_{CO}$ and $T < T_N$ as shown in Table 2. In the presence of the magnetic fields [8T, 5T, 1T], sharp and broad peaks

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Figure 13. Magnetic field verses resistivity $\rho(\Omega\text{-cm})$ at different temperature (300K,200K,100Kand 5K) for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.10$).

Figure 13, shows that on decreasing the temperature for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.10$), the compound first undergoes insulating to metallic phase at transition temperatures $T_p = 203$ and 209° respectively, then resuming the semiconducting behavior. A wide band centered between 70° to 140°K is observed as a consequence of charge ordering transition in the sample. at high temperature 300K the magnetic field verses resistivity $\rho(\Omega\text{-cm})$ will remain constant, while the temperature at 200K the magnetic field verses resistivity $\rho(\Omega\text{-cm})$ will slightly decrease, moreover, decreasing in temperature leads to increasing in magnetic field and increasing in verses resistivity $\rho(\Omega\text{-cm})$ till it reaches 20.

Figure 14. Magnetic field verses resistivity $\rho(\Omega\text{-cm})$ at different temperature (300K,200K,100Kand 5K) for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.15$).

Figure 14, shows that on decreasing the temperature for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.15$), the compound first undergoes insulating to metallic phase at transition temperatures $T_p = 203$ and 209o respectively, then resuming the semiconducting behavior. A wide band centered between 70o to 140oK is observed as a consequence of charge ordering transition in the sample. At high temperature 300K the magnetic field verses resistivity $\rho(\Omega\text{-cm})$ will remain constant, while the temperature at 200K the magnetic field verses resistivity $\rho(\Omega\text{-cm})$ will slightly decrease, moreover, decreasing in temperature leads to increasing in magnetic field and increasing in verses resistivity $\rho(\Omega\text{-cm})$ till it reaches more than 20. The strong increment of the resistivity with decreasing temperature can be described by the Mott's variable (VRH) model[35]. It is assume that the charge carries move along a path described by the optimal pair hopping from one localized state to another.

CONCLUSION

We have systemically investigated the structural and electronic transport properties for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.10$ and 0.15) and our finding may be summarized as follows:

We have studied the crystal structure using x-ray diffraction technique with the help of POWDER-X software we have determined the lattice parameters, unit cell volume, crystallite size and crystal symmetry for different compositions. We have found that, the unit cell volume of the sample decreases with the increase in Te concentration, the crystallite size increase with the increase in Te concentration, it has rhombohedral (hexagonal crystal symmetry). The temperature dependent resistivity $\rho(T)$ plots for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.10$ and 0.15) has been studied, on decreasing the temperature these compounds first undergo insulating to metallic phase transition at transition temperatures $T_p=203$ and 209oK respectively, then resuming the semiconducting behavior, a wide band centered between 70 to 140oK is observed as a consequence of charge ordering transition in both the samples.

The samples are found to be in single phase. The charge ordering transition temperature of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x\text{MnO}_3$ is enhanced with in Te concentration ($T_{co}=125\text{o}$ to 135oK), while the magneto resistance is suppressed slightly. Below and above the CO transition temperature, the transport behavior is dominated by Mott's variable range hopping (VRH) mechanism.

The magneto resistance as a function of temperature is also studied in the presence of magnetic of the magnetic fields, sharp and broad peaks can be attributed to the co-existence of the antiferromagnetic and ferromagnetic clusters, contributing the spatially metallic and insulating areas in the studied temperature.

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